

IMPROVEMENT OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES BY USE OF INTERLEAF FILMS

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ABSTRACT

An attempt was performed to reduce the free edge interlaminar stresses in the quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates by incorporating interleaf films between plies and thus to improve the mechanical properties of these materials. Material investigated is a $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate. The specimens were fabricated from unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg sheet and polyethylene based film as an interleaf material. CFRP laminate with interleaf films were produced using a vacuum bagging/autoclave curing technique. Both the static tests and fatigue tests were conducted to investigate the validity of the method involved.

As a result, this material has shown to increase the ultimate load and to improve the tensile strength reliability. Fatigue test results suggested that the CFRP laminate with interleaf films is promising to exhibit a high fatigue performance, if we have only chosen successfully the optimum incorporation location of interleaf into interlayers. In addition, the effect of visco-elastic properties of the interleaf material on the mechanical performance of these laminates is discussed in this paper. Discussion is also made on the fracture appearance in the different laminate in which the incorporation interfaces are changed variously.

Keywords: Delamination, Interleaf, CFRP, Quasi-isotropic laminate, Edge effect, Strength, Fatigue.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates are known to develop the interlaminar stress concentrations near the free edge region. Such a free edge delamination under loading in the plane of the laminate is a unique problem to laminated composites. This type of delamination significantly reduces static strength as well as fatigue resistance of such laminates¹. Interlaminar stresses are caused either by a poisson's ratio mismatch between adjacent laminae or by shear-extension coupling between dissimilarly oriented laminae. These interlaminar stresses are very high near free edges in the laminate.

In the present work, an attempt was performed to reduce the free edge interlaminar stresses in the laminate by incorporating interleaf films between plies and thus to improve the mechanical properties of these materials. In our previous work², we have shown that these laminates exhibit a high vibration damping capability. It was also shown that these laminates are promising to be excellent in static load carrying capability and tensile fatigue performance if we have only chosen successfully the optimum incorporation location of interleaf into interlayers. Thus in the present work, investigation was performed on the mechanical properties of the interleafed quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminate, with a

special emphasis on the optimum design of interply locations to incorporate the interleaf films for the particular requirement such as static strength, fatigue properties and so on.

2. SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

The specimens were fabricated from unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepreg sheet (T800/#2500, TORAY Industries, Inc.) and polyethylene based interleaf films (NEC & Mitsui Petrochemical Ind., Ltd.). Two kinds of polyethylene based films with different viscoelastic properties were used as the interleaf materials. Figure 1 gives an example of viscoelastic properties for the interleaf film. These properties were measured at 96Hz vibration. The maximum value of loss tangent was about 0.9 at room temperature. The glass transition temperatures in the other type of interleaf films were 50°C.

The interleaf films were approximately 70µm thick in both cases and were sandwiched between thermo-adhesive surface layers. CFRP laminates with interleaf films were produced using a vacuum bagging/autoclave curing technique. After cutting and lay-up of the required stacking sequence (see Figure 2), the laminates were cured in an autoclave for 3 hours at 130°C. A postcure process were conducted for melting the thermo-adhesive surface layer of the interleaf film. The cure cycles is shown in Figure 3, where the temperature and applied pressure histories are depicted.

Figure 2 Specimen lay-up process.

Figure 1 Viscoelastic properties for interleaf film.

Figure 3 Cure cycle diagram for specimens.

Figure 4 shows the stacking sequence for the various laminates prepared for the present work. The Type I specimen is a conventional CFRP laminates with symmetric $[0/\pm 45/90]$ lay-up, which has no interleaf layer. Type II through Type VIII were the CFRP laminates with interleaf films where the incorporation location of the interleaf is varied in each type. Type II has one interleaf film placed in its middle interlayer. In Type III interleaf films were incorporated in every interlayers. Type IV through Type VI have two interleaf films where the incorporated location of interleafs into interlayers are different in each case. Type VII has three interleaf films and Type VIII has four interleaf films. Cured specimen thickness were from $1.3\mu\text{m}$ to $1.8\mu\text{m}$. The surface of these specimens appeared generally very smooth, flat and uniform, equivalent to a conventional CFRP (Type I). A cross-sectional view of a Type III sample is given in Figure 5. Microscopic observation of layer structure, composed of CFRP and interleaf material, shows no debonding between layers and good consolidation. Test pieces were kept for two days or more prior to testing under constant conditions of 296K in temperature and 65% in humidity.

0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°
+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°
-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°
90°	90°	90°	90°	90°	90°	90°	90°
90°	90°	90°	90°	90°	90°	90°	90°
-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°	-45°
+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°	+45°
0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°	0°
Type I	Type II	Type III	Type IV	Type V	Type VI	Type VII	Type VIII

Figure 4 Stacking sequence for various CFRP laminates.

Figure 5 Cross-sectional view of Type III laminate.

Instron 4206 testing machine were used for static tension and compression tests. The tension and compression tests were conducted at 2mm/min and 0.5mm/min, respectively. Fatigue tests were conducted by an electro-hydraulic fatigue testing machine at the frequency of 10Hz. Fatigue tests were performed either under the repeated tension loading or under repeated compression loading. Cyclic stress ratio, R, representing a ratio of minimum stress to maximum stress was fixed to 0.1 and 10 for respective fatigue testing of tension loading and compression loading.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Static Strength Properties

As mentioned above, two kinds of interleaf materials whose glass transition temperature, T_g are different each other were used for this work. First, the tensile test results for the quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates with interleaf film whose T_g is in the vicinity of room temperature are listed in Table 1. Type II, Type IV, Type VI and Type VIII specimens, whose ultimate load (U_L) values are 26.4kN, 26.1kN, 26.4kN and 26.1kN have 4 and 5% larger U_L value, in comparison with the conventional CFRP value, 25.2kN. The largest U_L value was obtained in the Type VII specimen. The U_L value was 27.1kN (8% increase). The coefficient of variation (Cv), which is related to the

tensile strength reliability, is also listed in Table 1. The C_v values for CFRP/interleaf laminates, except for the Type III sample, are lower than that for Type I sample. This result suggests that the CFRP/interleaf laminates have high reliability, in regard to tensile strength.

The fracture mode for CFRP/interleaf laminates was found to be quite different from that for conventional CFRP. In conventional CFRP, the delaminations between -45° and 90° angle layers were generated at about 80% load of U_L . Figure 6 shows a ultrasonic C-scan results for Type I sample. The ultimate failure occurred in a catastrophic fashion with multiple longitudinal splits (broom straw effect). Similar delaminations were observed only in Type VI specimens. Another CFRP/interleaf laminate indicates no delamination between layers, even when loaded to 80% U_L . Ultrasonic C-scan inspection and fracture appearance revealed that the fracture process is remarkably different in each laminate. Dominant failure mode in each laminate depends strongly upon the location of interlayer, in which the interleaf films are incorporated. That means, we can change the failure mode in CFRP laminate by choosing the most appropriate interplies to incorporate the interleaf films. Experimental results indicate that interleaf film incorporated at the $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface can suppress the delamination damage in the CFRP laminate. On the other hand, an interleaf film is effective for suppressing the multiple splitting in the 0° angle layer, when it has been sandwiched between 0° and 45° layers.

Table 1 Tensile properties of various types of laminates with interleaf films ($T_g=R.T.$)

Specimen	Ultimate load	Load ratio	Coefficient of variation
	U_L (kN)	$U_L/U_{L(Type I)}$	C_v (%)
Type I	25.2	1.00	5.7
Type II	26.4	1.05	3.1
Type III	22.9	0.91	6.5
Type IV	26.1	1.04	4.3
Type V	25.1	1.00	2.8
Type VI	26.4	1.05	4.9
Type VII	27.1	1.08	1.4
Type VIII	26.1	1.04	1.8

Figure 6 Ultrasonic inspection result for Type I laminate.

Table 2 Effect of interleaf materials on tensile properties of CFRP/interleaf laminates.

Specimen	Ultimate load	Load ratio	Coefficient of variation
	U_L (kN)	$U_L/U_{L(Type I)}$	C_v (%)
Type I ₂	26.3	1.00	4.0
Type IV ₂	30.2	1.15	0.6
Type V ₂	24.7	0.94	2.1
Type VI ₂	27.1	1.03	1.2

Table 2 shows tensile test results for Type IV and Type VI specimens, in which the interleaf films with glass transition temperature of 50°C are used. Subscript H for the type of specimen signifies the interleaf films of the kind. Again, improvements in tensile properties and its reliability are observed both in Type IV_H and Type VI_H.

Tensile test results will now be shown for the quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates with sixteen layers. As shown in Figure 7, the number of layers is twice as large as above-mentioned specimen and lamination is double repetition for each angle layer. Subscript 2 signifies this type of laminates. Much more remarkable increase (15%) in tensile properties was obtained for Type IV₂ specimen as listed in Table 3.

Figure 7 Stacking sequence for 16plies CFRP/interleaf laminates.

Table 3 Effect of number of layers on tensile properties of CFRP/interleaf laminates.

Specimen	Ultimate load	Load ratio	Coefficient of variation
	U _L (kN)	U _L /U _{L(Type I)}	C _v (%)
Type I	25.2	1.00	5.7
Type IV	26.1	1.04	4.3
Type IV _H	27.0	1.07	4.8
Type VI	26.4	1.05	4.9
Type VI _H	26.5	1.05	2.0

3.2. Fatigue Properties

Figure 8 shows a comparison of the fatigue properties under tensile fatigue loading for the various types of CFRP/interleaf laminates, in which the maximum cyclic stress was plotted as a function of the number of cycles to fatigue failure. As a result, Type IV exhibits longer fatigue life when compared with Type I. The reason for this improvement of fatigue resistance in Type IV is considered to be due to the result of suppressing the delamination damage. On the other hand, fatigue life for Type IV_H decreased in comparison with Type I. Fracture of Type IV_H happened in a catastrophic fashion. This suggests that visco-elastic properties of interleaf material affects significantly the fatigue fracture process in CFRP/interleaf laminate. When the CFRP/interleaf laminate is subjected to cyclic loading, ductility of interleaf material in service temperature, which reflects the glass transition temperature will probably be a key in fatigue performance.

Compressive fatigue properties for Type I₂, Type IV₂, Type V₂ and Type VI₂ are compared in Figure 9. Again, fatigue properties for Type IV₂ was clearly improved in comparison with Type I₂,

conventional CFRP laminate. Figure 10 shows fracture appearances for Type I₂ and Type IV₂. It is observed that delamination damage between -45° and 0° layers has been suppressed successfully until final failure in Type IV₂. It should be pointed out here that Type IV laminate which is a CFRP laminate with interleaf films between -45° and 0° layers enhances not only the static load carrying capability but also the fatigue resistance either under tensile fatigue or under compressive fatigue loadings, as a result of suppressing the onset and propagation of delamination damage. In this meaning, fracture process of CFRP/interleaf laminate can be actively changed by choosing appropriate interplies to incorporate the interleaf films. Such a active control of fracture mode in CFRP laminate by use of interleaf films is undoubtedly a important concept and has a great potential for the optimum utilization of this material. It is emphasized in conclusion that the optimum interlayer location to incorporate interleaf films should be judged totally from the standpoints of static load carrying capability, fatigue performance, vibration damping capability² and so on.

Figure 8 Comparison of tensile fatigue properties for various types of CFRP/interleaf laminates.

Figure 9 Comparison of compressive fatigue properties for 16plies CFRP/interleaf laminates.

Type I₂

Type IV₂

Figure 10 Fracture appearances under compressive fatigue loading for Type I₂ and Type IV₂.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present investigation on quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminate with interleaf films led to the following conclusions:

1. The CFRP/interleaf laminate has been shown to increase the ultimate load and to improve the tensile strength reliability.
2. Interleaf films incorporated at $-45^{\circ}/90^{\circ}$ interface can suppress the delamination damage in $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ carbon/epoxy laminate. On the other hand, an interleaf film is effective for suppressing the multiple splitting in the 0° angle layer, when it has been sandwiched between 0° and 45° layers.
3. It was clarified in the present work that the mechanical properties of the CFRP/interleaf laminate depends upon the interlayer locations to incorporate interleaf films and visco-elastic properties of interleaf material.

Delamination suppression concept by use of interleaf films is concluded to have a good potential for significantly increasing both static strength and fatigue life of delamination-susceptible laminates. Determination of optimum incorporation location of interleaf and selection of the most appropriate interleaf material corresponded to the actual requirements for mechanical performance, is a most important key for a successful application of this concept.

References

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